

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15485034>

TISSUE RESPONSE OF NEWBORN RATS TO THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE THYROID GLAND IN LACTATING FEMALE RATS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the results of an experimental study investigating the response of newborn rat tissues to excess and deficiency of thyroxine in the bodies of lactating female rats, as well as the morphofunctional state of the thyroid gland in suckling offspring. The findings indicate that both an excess and a deficiency of thyroxine in maternal milk result in significant alterations in various biochemical parameters in the offspring.

Key words: *thyroxine excess and deficiency, milk, pituitary thyrotrophs, thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), thyroid gland, mitochondrial α -glycerophosphate oxidase, suckling rats.*

Introduction. Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in metabolism due to their pronounced regulatory influence on its fundamental functions. The first indications of the possible transfer of thyroid hormones from a lactating mother to her offspring via milk appeared as early as the late 1950s [7]. It was demonstrated that when thyroxine (T4) is administered intravenously to lactating rats, it appears in their milk, with T4 concentrations reaching 38–74% of those found in plasma. It is assumed that thyroid hormones are transferred into breast milk, enter the body of the suckling pups, and may exert a regulatory effect on their thyroid function. Similar conclusions were drawn by researchers studying the levels of T4 and triiodothyronine (T3) in the breast milk of humans and primates [9]. Moreover, studies of human milk have revealed a significant increase in these hormones as lactation progresses, particularly during the transition from colostrum to mature milk. Thus, literature data suggest that thyroid hormones are secreted into human breast milk and may influence the developing organism of the newborn. At the same time, this phenomenon requires further investigation.

Objective of the Study. To evaluate the effect of excess and deficiency of thyroxine in lactating rats on tissue responses in newborns and on the morphofunctional state of the thyroid gland in suckling rat pups in an experimental setting.

Materials and Methods. The experiments were conducted on pregnant and lactating rats and their offspring. A reduced level of thyroid hormones was achieved through thyroidectomy. The thyroidectomy was performed under ether anesthesia using a standard technique [2]. An elevated level of thyroid hormones was induced by daily administration of L-thyroxine at a dose of 100 µg per 100 g of body weight in the morning.

To assess tissue sensitivity to insulin, in some of the pups, after euthanasia under ether anesthesia, the diaphragm was isolated and placed in Medium 199 containing insulin at a concentration of 1 mU/ml. After one hour of incubation, glucose concentration in the incubation medium was measured using the orthotoluidine method of Hultman, modified by Hivarinene-Nikkila, and glycogen content in the tissue was determined using the anthrone reagent. The α -glycerophosphate oxidase activity of liver mitochondria, obtained by differential centrifugation, was measured using a polarographic method. To study the morphofunctional state of the thyroid gland, morphometric analysis was performed on the thyroid glands of suckling rat pups. Thyrotropin (TSH) levels were determined using a radioimmunoassay. Depending on the experimental series, the suckling pups were euthanized in accordance with ethical standards on days 1, 5, 6, 8, 10, 15, 17, and 21 of postnatal development.

The obtained numerical data were statistically processed using Student's *t*-test.

Results and Discussion. The spectrum of biological effects of T4 and T3 is extremely broad, and receptors for these hormones are found in virtually all organs and tissues. Thyroid hormones exert positive chronotropic and inotropic effects on the heart, promote lipolysis, accelerate gas exchange in the lungs, increase blood flow and glomerular filtration in the kidneys, thereby enhancing diuresis, and stimulate redox reactions in many organs and tissues [3]. In this study, one of the criteria used to evaluate the influence of milk-borne thyroid hormones on the suckling pups was the state of carbohydrate metabolism. It is well known that thyroid hormones regulate the expression of genes in hepatocytes involved in gluconeogenesis, glycogen metabolism, and insulin action. T3 is known to have a regulatory effect on the enzyme phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase, which plays a key role in the cascade of gluconeogenic reactions [8, 10]. It also increases the expression of glucose-6-phosphatase mRNA, the terminal enzyme in gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis, which catalyzes the hydrolysis of glucose-6-phosphate to produce free glucose [11, 12].

Thyroidectomy in lactating rats led to a decrease in T4 content in the maternal milk as well as in the serum of the suckling rat pups. Conversely, administration of T4 to lactating mothers resulted in dose-dependent changes in T4 concentrations in both the milk and the serum of the newborn pups. Following maternal thyroidectomy, a significant reduction was observed in the blood glucose concentration (from 81.0 to 62.0 mg%) and hepatic glycogen content (from 1.0 to 0.336 g%) in the offspring. Administration of thyroxine to the lactating mothers normalized glucose and glycogen levels in the pups.

An investigation of tissue sensitivity to insulin revealed that when insulin was added to the incubation medium containing muscle tissue (diaphragm) isolated from the offspring of thyroidectomized dams, there was neither an increase in glucose uptake nor an enhancement in glycogen synthesis (Table 1).

Table 1.

Effect of insulin (1 mU/ml) on glycogen accumulation in the diaphragm and glucose depletion in the incubation medium in suckling rat pups born to sham-operated and thyroidectomized (T/E), and T4-treated thyroidectomized (T/E + T4) lactating rats

Group	Glucose, mg%		Glycogen, g%	
	Control	+ Insulin	Control	+ Insulin
Sham T/E	242 ± 10.0 (n=15)	185 ± 13.3 (n=5)	0.226 ± 0.04 (n=12)	0.326 ± 0.032 (n=12)
T/E	246 ± 12.1 (n=14)	242 ± 11.0 (n=14)	0.203 ± 0.013 (n=12)	0.198 ± 0.14 (n=12)
T/E + T4	210 ± 11.2 (n=6)	180 ± 10.1 (n=6)	0.225 ± 0.03 (n=6)	0.315 ± 0.02 (n=6)

Note: The studies were conducted on day 6 after maternal thyroidectomy, i.e., on day 8 of lactation; the number of samples is indicated in parentheses.

Thus, the obtained data indicate a reduced sensitivity of the diaphragm in suckling rat pups from thyroidectomized dams to insulin. It is well known that hypothyroidism is one of the conditions that can lead to the development of insulin resistance [4, 5, 6].

Studies of pituitary thyrotropic activity revealed that the level of thyrotropin in pups from thyroidectomized mothers was slightly higher (22.4 ± 3.02%) compared to those from sham-operated (control) mothers (18.8 ± 2.74%). This was reflected in the morphological structure of the thyroid gland. Specifically, indicators of thyrocyte

functional activity were higher in suckling pups from lactating thyroidectomized dams (Table 2).

The trend toward increased pituitary thyrotropic function in the experimental group of pups suggests the involvement of the pituitary gland in the regulation of thyroid status in rat pups aged 3 to 8 days.

It is known that α -glycerophosphate oxidase is a thyroxine-dependent enzyme and, along with other enzymes, plays an important role in the body by participating in various metabolic processes [1]. Therefore, the activity of this enzyme may serve as an indicator of changes in thyroid hormone concentrations.

Table 2.

Morphological indicators of functional activity of the thyroid gland in suckling rat pups from thyroidectomized lactating dams

Day		Surgical group	Follicular Inner Diameter, μm	Thyroid Epithelial Height, μm	Colloid Resorption Score	Functional Activity Index (FAI)	1* FAI
Of development	Post operative						
5	3	Sham	6,8	2,48	1,21	2,20	0,43
		T/E	9,0	2,57	1,30	2,69	0,33
8	6	Sham	11,0	3,2	1,18	2,91	0,34
		T/E	8,0	3,8	1,20	1,75	0,57
14	12	Sham	17	3,7	1,3	3,53	0,28
		T/E	18	3,9	1,3	3,60	0,27

*Considering that the value of the functional activity index (FAI) is inversely proportional to the level of function, for the convenience of analysis, we present the reciprocal values of FAI (1/FAI).

Thyroidectomy of the lactating dam led to a decrease in the activity of α -glycerophosphate oxidase in the liver mitochondria of pups by more than 50% compared to the control group by the 10th day of life (Table 3). As the lactation period progressed, enzyme activity increased from 0.105 to 0.288 $\mu\text{mol O}_2$ per minute per 1 mg of protein. Thyroidectomy of the lactating rat led to a marked decrease in the α -glycerophosphate oxidase activity of the liver mitochondria of pups on the 8th and 10th days of lactation. From the 15th day of lactation, enzyme activity in the experimental

group began to recover to the control level, and by the 21st day, it no longer differed from the control level. Changes in the α -glycerophosphate oxidase activity of liver mitochondria in pups an enzyme that serves as a criterion for the peripheral action of thyroid hormones indicate that the organism of newborn pups significantly responds to changes in the hormonal status of the lactating mother during lactation.

Table 3.

Activity of α -glycerophosphate oxidase in liver mitochondria of pups from thyroidectomized rats

Day of lactation	Enzyme Activity ($\mu\text{mol O}_2$ per min per mg protein)		% of Control
	Control	Experimental	
8	0,105 \pm 0,0052	0,079 \pm 0,0048*	75
10	0,160 \pm 0,01	0,096 \pm 0,007*	60
15	0,170 \pm 0,01	0,119 \pm 0,01*	70
17	0,253 \pm 0,02	0,30 \pm 0,02	90
21	0,288 \pm 0,019	0,286 \pm 0,018	99

Note: * differences are statistically significant; the number of replicates in all series was 5.

The administration of T4 to lactating mothers contributed to the normalization of the response.

Conclusions. Considering the fact that thyroid hormones are transferred to the offspring through milk, it can be assumed that both a deficiency and an excess of thyroxine in maternal milk leads to noticeable changes in various biochemical parameters in the offspring.

A disturbed thyroid status of the lactating mother results in a decrease in the activity of mitochondrial α -glycerophosphate oxidase in the liver of the sucklings. In contrast, normalization of the maternal thyroid status leads to a normalization of the offspring's response.

The results of this study expand our understanding of the mechanisms underlying dysfunction within the "mother–newborn" functional system. They also highlight the most significant risk factors affecting the neonatal organism, enhance current knowledge about the role of biologically active compounds in milk during the early postnatal period, and support the physiological necessity at least for certain mammalian species of thyroid hormone transfer via milk.

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